

IMPORTANT FACTORS ENSURING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MOTHER TONGUE CLASSES IN GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION

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The teaching of the Uzbek language, which is considered the state language, in secondary general education schools is one of the most important socio-economic, educational, educational and developmental issues. Only a person who knows his native language perfectly and can easily use its beautiful, rich and colorful possibilities in speech can meet the demands of society.

Language exists in the human mind as a necessary social phenomenon. Therefore, learning it is convenient and easy in some aspects, while in some aspects it is difficult and complicated.

For a child who uses language as a social necessity, it is easier to learn it, but it is more difficult to master the art of using its rich possibilities in accordance with speech conditions. Teaching the pupils, who are the future of our republic, to these subtle secrets is considered the main requirement of teaching the mother tongue at school.

Therefore, Uzbek language education, which exists as hidden possibilities in the minds of students, faces the following main tasks: Uzbek language training in students to develop creativity, independent thinking, and verbalize the product of creative thought in accordance with the speech conditions. and should be focused on forming and developing the skills of correct, fluent expression in writing. Its effectiveness will be high only if the content of Uzbek language education is subordinated to these main goals. In the process of education, teaching the student to think logically is one of the important factors that ensure the effectiveness of education.

In the process of Uzbek language education, the child is trained to think logically, to express one's own thoughts in a logical sequence, and to be able to understand the

speech of others. For this, the main task is to develop the child's speech and regularly enrich his vocabulary.

The tasks assigned to the Uzbek language education in the primary school are multifaceted, they are aimed at intellectual and verbal development of students, expanding their knowledge about the environment, moral education, assimilation of knowledge, conscious self. It is directed to the formation of reading and writing skills, the skills of working with textbooks. Also, students are directed to think creatively, compose a sentence, and analyze its content. Analyzing texts and pictures that provide information about natural phenomena, animal and plant world, the past of our country, and our great ancestors, which are of interest to students, is considered one of the appropriate factors in expanding the range of logical thinking.

Organization of the lesson process using interdisciplinary communication in the primary school encourages students to be inquisitive, increases their interest in additional literature.

If we take the topic "Uzbekistan My Country" as an example, it can be studied in connection with all subjects. For example, "Motherland is a great word." The place where the navel blood of our grandfathers was spilled. Homeland is the house where we and you live. Our love for him begins with our mother." Also, it would be appropriate if the students' knowledge, skills and abilities were expanded by giving examples from the works of the spiritual heritage left by our ancestors, teaching from wise words and proverbs.

In the next paragraph of our graduation thesis, we will try to give brief methodological explanations on the formation of students' logical thinking and creative way of thinking in the process of Uzbek language education.

Cultivating the student's thinking is one of the main issues of Uzbek language education in UOT schools. In solving this issue, priority is given to creative tasks. Such tasks are system-learning tasks of exercises that are to be taught practically, or to be strengthened, and are selected in accordance with the topic of theoretical information. They should also meet the requirements of pedagogical technology, such as directing from simple to complex, from known to unknown, from easy to difficult. For example, making a conclusion about a linguistic phenomenon, brainstorming about the function of the hyphen in given pairs of words.

During the lesson, through creative tasks, students observe, compare, identify and group linguistic phenomena. Finally, as stated in the DTS, judgment is made with the help of the teacher on the given materials. According to scientists who have conducted special research on this problem, creative tasks that increase thinking

should first of all encourage the student to search, search, and find the unknown. Secondly, as the problem becomes more complicated, the student's mind and insight should gradually develop, and fourthly, it should be directed to the student's judgment, conclusion and generalization. Finally, in the work process, it is necessary to inform the student that his knowledge is not enough, to encourage him to acquire new knowledge.

Associate Professor Muhammad Saidov, candidate of philological sciences, came to the right conclusion about the final result of the educational process.

It should be noted that lessons on the phonetics, morphology, and lexicology parts of the language do not start with rules and definitions, but begin with the analysis of given sentences and words, gradually moving from one method of activity to another, for example, from observation to grouping, from comparison to It is structured in the form of identifying similarities and differences, forming generalizations from grouping. Such independent activities make it easier to understand the nature of the language phenomena being studied. The student acquires knowledge and skills through hard work.

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